

EFFECT OF SELECTED SELF-BOOSTING ACTIVITIES ON THE SELF-CONFIDENCE OF DIFFERENTLY ABLED SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

Mukesh Kumar¹ & Dr. Rakesh Kumar²

¹Ph. D Research Scholar, Dept. of Education, Himachal Pradesh University, Shimla, India.

Email: mukkulathi138@gmail.com

²Assistant Professor, Dept. of Education, Himachal Pradesh University, Shimla, India.

Email: researchdrakesh@gmail.com

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Abstract

The present investigation studies on the result of certain self-boosting activities on the self-confidence of differently abled secondary school students. These adolescents frequently deal with certain social and psychological issues that can impede their growth both personally and academically. The present investigation follows the quasi-experimental research design. A structured package comprising self-affirmation practices, goal-setting tasks, and peer-interaction activities was developed and implemented among the experimental group. The study's sample size was 30 hearing and speech impaired students from a selected school. Using a quasi-experimental, pre-test and post-test control group design, the data were analysed by using t-test which determine changes in self-confidence levels of differently abled secondary school students. The results revealed a considerable improvement in self-confidence of students who participated in the intervention, suggesting the effectiveness of self-boosting strategies in fostering psychological empowerment in differently abled adolescents.

Keywords: *Self-Confidence, Differently Abled Students, Self-Boosting Activities, Experimental Research, Intervention Strategies.*

Introduction

students with disabilities often encounter marginalization, limited opportunities, and low self-esteem, therefore self-confidence is extremely important for their overall development. Education is increasingly recognizing the need to nurture self-worth in such

students through targeted interventions. This study aims to assess how structured self-boosting activities designed to promote self-belief, autonomy, and resilience can positively influence the self-confidence of differently abled secondary school students.

Building self-confidence in differently abled students is not just about fulfilling their academic needs, but also about developing an internal belief system that encourages them to take initiative, get involved socially, and persevere in the face of adversity. These adolescents frequently adopt negative cultural beliefs, which can have a significant influence on their psychological wellness and academic achievement. Structured self-improvement activities such as guided statements of belief, establishing objectives activities, motivated interactions with peers, and exposure of effective role models serve as essential psychological tools for mitigating these negative consequences. When used in an equitable and empathic learning environment, by helping students to alter their own identities from one of limitation to one of possibility, these activities assist in the establishment of a positive self-concept. Through such customized techniques, the system of learning has the potential to reshape the opportunities of differently abled students, allowing them to realize their strengths, express their objectives, and actively participate in their respective academic and social domains.

Background of the study

Several experimental research have studied the impact of various educational and psychological treatments on students' self-confidence. Sedeghi and Ganji (2020) studied the effects of cooperative learning on class engagement, self-esteem, and confidence among Iranian university students were investigated. Using ANCOVA to analyse data in a sample of 30 students assigned to control and experimental groups, the study discovered significant improvements in self-confidence and classroom involvement as a result of cooperative learning. The researchers recommended comparable strategies for high school and college students.

In another experimental study, Gagan (2020), The Small Group Teaching Method (SGTM) was investigated to determine how it influenced learning outcomes, interaction with peers in, self-concept, and self-confidence within ninth-grade students. A quasi-experimental study with 100 participants found that small group training greatly increased learners' self-confidence and self-concept. The findings pointed out that SGTM could be an effective technique for increasing student performance in a variety of academic disciplines.

Mona (2018) In addition, a quasi-experimental study was done to determine the influence of collaborative teaching on ninth-grade students' self-confidence, peer

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connections, and English grammar ability. The study, which included 120 participants, utilized a t-test to analyse the data and discovered that cooperative learning had a substantial influence on self-confidence as well as academic accomplishment, especially when the treatment was extended for a longer period of time. The study addressed how gender and treatment duration influence outcomes.

These studies collectively support the effectiveness of interactive and collaborative learning strategies in boosting self-confidence across different educational levels and contexts. They underscore the importance of structured interventions tailored to students' psychological and academic needs, especially for those who may face additional barriers to learning and self-development.

Significance of the Study

This study fills a critical research gap by examining the role of structured self-boosting interventions in promoting self-confidence among differently abled students. It provides significant knowledge for teachers, educators who develop curriculum, and authorities working toward inclusive education. The findings can inform the integration of psychological support programs within regular curricula, thereby enhancing the educational outcomes and personal growth of students with disabilities.

Statement of the Problem

The intention of the present investigation was to explore the “Effect of selected self-boosting activities on the self-confidence of differently abled secondary school students”.

Objective

- To study the significant difference in mean pre-test and post-test scores on Self-confidence of Differently Abled Secondary School Students within Experimental and control group.

Hypothesis

- There will be no significant difference in mean pre-test and post-test scores on Self-confidence of Differently Abled Secondary School Students within Experimental and control group.

Delimitation of the study

- The study is restricted to the selected self-boosting activities on the self-confidence developed by the investigator by himself only.
- The study is restricted to only one selected special school of Himachal Pradesh.
- The study is further confined to the differently abled secondary school students only.

Methodology Used

The study employed a pre-test post-test control group experimental design, which is widely used in quasi-experimental research. The self-boosting package included activities such as positive affirmation journaling, group encouragement games, success storytelling sessions, and confidence-building tasks. Both the experimental and control groups were given the same standardized self-confidence questionnaire developed by Gupta and Lakhani (2018).

Sample and Sampling

The sample comprised 30 differently abled secondary school students (hearing and speech impaired), selected using purposive sampling from one special school of district Shimla in Himachal Pradesh. The students were split into two groups random: the experimental group (n = 14) and the control group (n = 16). Care was taken to ensure similarity in terms of age, severity of disability, and type of disability across both groups.

Variables of the Study

In the present investigation, selected self-boosting activities was taken as an independent variable while Self-Confidence was taken as dependent variable.

Tool Used

In the present study, Self-Confidence Scale by Gupta and Lakhani (2018) and Self-developed Self-Fortifying Package for Differently Abled Secondary School Students tools were used.

Experimental procedure

The sample consisted of 30 secondary school students who were randomly assigned to two equal groups: 14 students participating in the experiment and 16 students participating in the control group. The experiment was conducted using a pre-test and post-test design. Self-confidence tests were given to both the Experimental and Control groups before and after the intervention. Self-boosting activities were undertaken for four weeks in the experimental group, while the therapy group received just the experimental group. However, regular activities were delivered to the students in the Control group.

Statistical Technique Used

As presently conducted investigation is experimental in nature and to achieve the objectives of the study the investigator used t-test as a statistical technique for analysis the data.

Data Analysis

In order to test the stated hypothesis, a paired sample *t*-test was used to compare the mean scores of pre-tests and post-test of self-confidence levels within the experimental and control groups. The statistical findings are summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Comparison of Pre-test and Post-test Mean Scores on Self-confidence of Differently Abled Secondary School Students within Experimental and Control Groups

Group	N	Test Type	Mean Score	SD	SED	t-value	Level of Significance
Experimental Group	14	Pre-test	168.86	20.24	7.42	3.93	Significant
		Post-test	198.00	18.98			
Control Group	16	Pre-test	165.44	20.59	7.40	4.14	Significant
		Post-test	171.25	21.25			

Table 1 revealed a statistically significant difference between the mean pre-test and post-test scores on self-confidence for both the experimental and control groups. In the experimental group, the mean self-confidence score increased from 168.86 to 198.00, with a *t*-value of 3.93, which is significant at both 0.05 and 0.01 levels of significance. Similarly, in the control group, the mean score increased from 165.44 to 171.25, with a *t*-value of 4.14, also significant at both levels of significance.

These findings indicated that both groups showed improvement in self-confidence from pre-test to post-test. However, the improvements in the group receiving the treatment (experimental group) is significantly greater as compared to the individuals in the control group, suggesting that the intervention provided to the experimental group will definitely be contributed positively in boosting self-confidence among secondary school students.

Therefore, the null hypothesis stating that "*There will be no significant difference in mean pre-test and post-test scores on self-confidence of differently abled secondary school students within experimental and control groups*" is **rejected**, as significant differences were observed in both groups.

Major Findings

1. Both the experimental and control groups exhibited a statistically significant improvement in self-confidence from pre-test to post-test, indicating overall progress among differently abled secondary school students.
2. The experimental group demonstrated a notably greater increase in self-confidence compared to the control group, suggesting that the intervention had a positive and meaningful impact on enhancing self-confidence levels.

Educational Implications

1. Design and introduce specific interventions to enhance self-confidence among differently abled students, as these have shown to be effective.
2. Use inclusive teaching strategies that actively engage differently abled learners to boost their self-esteem, self-confidence and participation.
3. Incorporate self-confidence modules or activities into special education curricula through policy-level changes to ensure continuous support.
4. Provide teacher training focused on understanding and addressing the emotional and psychological needs of differently abled students.

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